

THE USAGE OF IDIOMATIC EXPRESSIONS WITH PROPER NAMES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

This article shows that there are so many idiomatic expressions among people, each with its own theme and meaning. There are many idioms involving proper names among them. Idiomatic expressions involving proper names add more splendor and color to the language; they are more commonly used by people with a large vocabulary and broad outlook.

Key words: idiomatic expressions, proper names, wisdom, language, nationality.

Introduction. Idiomatic expressions containing proper names entered English through folklore, prose and poetry, myths, fairy tales, fables, songs, slang, and other sources. Many idioms with proper names are familiar to people of various nationalities, and it is natural for English learners to want to know how to say those colorful expressions in English. Proper names are critical to our comprehension of linguistic 'aboutness' or reference. For example, the name-bearer relation is a good candidate for the reference relation of paradigm: it gives us our first impression of the relation and guides our thinking about it. Proper names have been the focus of philosophical attention for this and other reasons. Proper names, on the other hand, are as contentious as they are conceptually fundamental.

However, it should be noted that idioms with proper names are rarely used in speech or writing. For example, we all know such expressions as "Pyrrhic victory" (A pyrrhic victory is a victory that comes at a great cost, perhaps making the ordeal to win not worth it. It relates to Pyrrhus, a king of Epirus who defeated the Romans in 279 BCE but lost many of his troops) or "as wise as Solomon" (Exceptionally wise, discerning, or sound in judgement. A reference to the King Solomon, renowned for his wisdom). But how often do we use them? In general, more neutral phrases are preferred in everyday speech. Proper name idioms are typically informal in nature. Some of them are slang, making them inappropriate for formal speech and writing; additionally, slang idioms frequently have undesirable additional meanings. Some idioms with people's names, nationality names, city names, or country names may be perceived as offensive stereotypes and clichés; such idioms should be avoided.

Main part. The following lists contain examples of English idiomatic expressions with proper names. They include still-in-use idioms as well as some bookish or outdated expressions.

Idioms with people's names

Before you could say Jack Robinson-very quickly;

Several citations use Jack Robinson to describe quickness of thought or deed. e.g. She'd jumped into the car and driven away before you could say Jack Robinson. The standard usage is "(something is done) faster than you can say Jack Robinson," or "before you can say Jack Robinson." According to legend, Jack Robinson, an English gentleman from the early nineteenth century, changed his mind very quickly. Someone had to act quickly to catch him in a decision.

Doubting Thomas - skeptic; someone who refuses to believe in the absence of clear proof. e.g. He's such a doubting Thomas that unless he sees things through his eyes, he won't believe.

It refers to the Gospel of John's depiction of the apostle Thomas, who, according to John's account, refused to believe the resurrected Jesus appeared to the ten other apostles until he could see and feel Jesus' crucifixion wounds.

Every Tom, Dick, and Harry – any / every ordinary man. If every Tom, Dick, and Harry can do it, it confers no status.

The phrase "Tom, Dick, and Harry" refers to unspecified people. Although Brewer's Dictionary of Phrase and Fable defines the term to specify "a set of nobodies; persons of no note", the phrase most commonly occurs as "every Tom, Dick, and Harry", meaning everyone, and "any Tom, Dick, or Harry", meaning anyone. [Brewer; 675].

The phrase's origin is unknown. The phrase was first used in 1657 by the 17th-century English theologian John Owen. Owen told an Oxford University governing body that "our critical situation and our common interests were discussed out of journals and newspapers by every Tom, Dick, and Harry." In

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Elizabethan times, pairs of common male names, particularly Jack and Tom, Dick and Tom, or Tom and Tib, were frequently used generically. [Toon; no. 52].

Jack of all Trades – a person who can do many manual jobs;

This expression is used about a person who can do passable work at various tasks and a handy versatile person. e.g. My mother is a Jack of all trades; she learned how to do the repairs around the house; she does all of the housework and cooking; and she can even fix our computers.

Hobson's choice – a choice in which only one option is presented; take it or leave it; lack of choice. e.g. It's a case of Hobson's choice, because I'll lose my job if I don't agree to their terms.

Hobson's choice is a free choice in which only one option is presented. The term is frequently used to describe the illusion that multiple options are available. "I'll give you a choice: take it or leave it," the most well-known Hobson's choice, where "leaving it" is strongly undesirable.

The phrase is said to have originated with Thomas Hobson (1544–1631), a livery stable owner in Cambridge, England, who offered customers the option of taking the horse in his stall nearest to the door or taking none at all.

John Bull – a typical Englishman; the English people. e.g. His ruddy countenance and stout figure made him look a genuine John Bull.

John Bull, character typifying the English nation in John Arbuthnot's *The History of John Bull* (1712). In political cartoons and similar graphic works, John Bull is a national personification of the United Kingdom in general and England in particular. He is typically portrayed as a stout, middle-aged, country-dwelling, jolly, and matter of fact man.

Johnny on the spot – a person who is always present, always ready to perform a task or seize an opportunity. e.g. "When Jenny comes over, you need to be my Johnny on the Spot and make sure we have whatever he needs" .

The phrase 'Johnny On the Spot' refers to a person who is always available, ready, reliable, and willing to perform a duty or task without delay. The phrase "Johnny on the Spot" first appeared in the April 1896 issue of the *New York Sun*: "Johnny on the Spot: New Phrase Which Has Become Popular in New York." The phrase's exact origin is unknown, but it was most likely inspired by the phrase "Johnny is always on the spot when wanted." And this idiomatic expression with the proper name "Johnny" is still used among people when they talk to each other.

Conclusion. There are many idioms in English involving proper names. Most of them have a certain history and we can find many examples to these idiomatic expressions. The use of such idioms in language helps to make what we say more effective and brighter. Not everyone can use idioms involving a proper name, only people who know the language perfectly can use them when they are necessary.

Idioms, proverbs, and expressions are common in everyday life. They appear frequently in both written and spoken language. Because idioms do not always make literal sense, we will need to become acquainted with the meaning and usage of each idiom. That may appear to be a lot of work, but learning idioms is enjoyable, especially when comparing idioms in two or more languages.

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